

Solving for the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Using Scaling Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$ through scaling arguments if one makes the approximation that e may range from 0 to infinite. We obtained a differential-integral equation and used $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$ as a trial solution which solved the problem. Here we solve the problem directly without resort to a trial solution..

Scaling Argument

We begin with:

$$E_{ave} = \frac{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} p(e/T) e \, de}{\int c_1 \sqrt{e} p(e/T) \, de} \quad ((1))$$

If e ranges from 0 to infinite, which is an approximation, then:

$$E = \text{number} * T \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is in fact the ideal gas result and here we work in three dimensions, hence $c_1 \sqrt{e} \, de$ from $p^2 dp \propto \sqrt{e} \, de$. We absorb the various constants into c_1 .

$$\text{We then argue that if } T \rightarrow T+dT, \quad E(T+dT) = \text{number} * (T+dT) \quad ((3))$$

The 'number', however, involves integrals involving T and so we must replace T with $T+dT$ and show that at least the coefficient of dT goes to 0.

Replacing T with $T+dT$ and taking the coefficient of dT in ((1)) yields:

$$\int (-1) * \text{number} \, dp/dT \sqrt{e} \, de + \int e/T (-1/T) p \sqrt{e} \, de + \int (e/T) dp/dT \sqrt{e} \, de = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) must be zero so we drop c_1 . Now:

$$dp(e/T)/dT = dp/dy (-y/T) \quad \text{where } y=e/T \quad ((5)) \text{ so:}$$

$$0 = \int \{ (\text{number}) \, 1/T \, y \, dp/dy - 1/T \, y p - y y/T \, dp/dy \} \sqrt{e} \, de \quad ((6))$$

One may factor out $1/T$.

We suggest using integration by parts on the last term - $\int y y/T \, dp/dy$ i.e.

$$-\int y y/T \, dp/dy \sqrt{e} \, de = 2.5 \int y \sqrt{e} \, de \quad ((7))$$

Thus:

$$0 = -\text{number} * \int \sqrt{e} \, de - y \, dp/dy + 1.5 \int y p \sqrt{e} \, de \quad ((8))$$

One may consider:

$$-\text{number} * y \, dp/dy = 1.5 \, y p \quad ((9))$$

A solution is $p = \exp(-y)$, but only if $\text{number} = 1.5$ ((10))

To check this, one must go back to the definition of Eave to see that indeed for three dimensions:

$$E = 3/2 T \text{ constant where constant} = NR \quad ((11))$$

$p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$ is the solution to the problem as $\text{number} = 1.5$. Normalizing, one has the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution:

$$p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T) \quad ((12))$$

This direct calculation bypasses the approach of Part 1 of using a trial solution of $p(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. We obtain the MB distribution function directly from the scaling approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1, we suggested that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by using scaling arguments. We used the approximation of allowing e to range from 0 to infinite, which is the same approximation used in the local subset approach $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((13)) for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, and so argued that $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$, which follows directly for this approach, be used as a trial solution for the scaling condition ((4)). We found that $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$ satisfies ((4)). Here, we obtain $p(e)$ directly without using any trial solution and find again that $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$.